

Dr Ammar Anwer is a
Neurosurgeon with
expertise in Minimally
Invasive Neurosurgery
(Brain and Spine) and
Functional
Neurosurgery (Deep
Brain Stimulation, Spinal
Cord Stimulation)

CONTACT US

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Minimally Invasive Neurosurgery

LIGHTS, CAMERA, NEURONS

SCOPE OF SERVICES

MINIMALLY INVASIVE ENDOSCOPIC BRAIN SURGERY

Endoscopic surgery is either done through nose or through a small hole in skull (0.5cm). The following conditions are treated with endoscopic surgery;

1. Hydrocephalus
2. Pituitary Tumors

BRAIN ONCOLOGY

Brain tumors are treated utilizing microscopic surgical techniques. The aim of brain tumor surgery is to remove the maximal possible tumor while ensuring that the patient doesn't develop any new deficit. Brain oncological services are available for;

1. Primary Brain Tumor
2. Meta-static brain tumors

STEREOTACTIC BRAIN BIOPSY

Stereotactic brain tumor biopsy is a minimally invasive technique for diagnosing deep brain lesions, aspirations of cysts and hematomas. Dr Ammar Anwer performs stereotactic procedures using Inomed

RM & ZD frames. Procedure is done under local anesthesia and a small hole is drilled in skull. This procedure has sub-millimeter accuracy, and high diagnostic yield.

PERCUTANEOUS SPINE SURGERY

This is minimally invasive spine surgery which is done utilizing endoscope and special spine fixation instruments. There is minimal scarring and patient is discharged on the same evening. These services are available for;

1. Prolapsed intervertebral disc
2. Spine fractures

FUNCTIONAL NEUROSURGERY

Deep Brain Stimulation and Spinal Cord Stimulation surgical and IPG programming services are available with Dr Ammar Anwer for all FDA approved indications.

1. Medtronic Activa DBS system
2. St Jude's Medical Infinity DBS system
3. PINS Medical G102 DBS system
4. Medtronic Prime Advanced SCS system

NEED A CONSULT?
YOU CAN EITHER
SCHEDULE YOUR
APPOINTMENT FOR
CLINIC VISIT OR
CONSULT US ONLINE.

CONTACT:

